

Minutes EB25-1
Meeting of the SeqCode Executive Board
12 February 2025 @ 7h00 (EST)

Attendance

Maria Chuvochina (MC)	- Chair, Reconciliation Commission
Kostas Konstantinidis (KK)	- Chair, Standards Working Group
Anna-Louise Reysenbach (ALR)	- Vice Chair
Luis Miguel Rodriguez (LMR)	- Chair, Registry Working Group
Iain Sutcliffe (IS)	- Chair, Legislative Commission
Fanus Venter (FV)	- Secretary
Barny Whitman (BW)	- Chair
Fengping Wang (FW)	- Member without portfolio

Apologies

Phil Hugenholtz (PH)	- Member without portfolio
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1. Welcome

BW welcomed the members of the Executive Board.

2. Additions to the Agenda

Definition of membership

3. Matters Arising/Action points from the previous meeting

New and ongoing action items from previous meeting

- 1. FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved.*
Completed
- 2. FV to interact with Kelly Wrighton to offer our assistance in supporting or presenting a SeqCode session at any of the regional conferences.*
Completed
- 3. PH to request the ISME Board to reconsider the requirement that ISME funding cannot be used for the payment of persons assisting with the development of the Registry.*
Ongoing
- 4. IS to add a note indicating that this version of the SeqCode is an update and reflects all changes in the SeqCode to date.*
Completed
- 5. LMR to provide IS with Version 1.03, which corrected some small errors, so IS can ensure that these were incorporated into Version 1.1.0.*
Completed
- 6. IS to share the revised version of the Code with MC, FV and LMR for posting on the various platforms.*
Completed
- 7. LMR to supply images of the SeqCode logo to be used as a banner for the group's LinkedIn contact page.*

Completed

8. *FV to draft a text for a Wikipedia article on the SeqCode and circulated it amongst the EB.*
Ongoing
9. *BW to prepare a draft proposal for possible amendments to the code to include paratypes for further discussion by the EB.*
BW started developing some proposals, effort ongoing.
10. *FV to inform the Bergey's Manual Trust of our decision to participate in the proposed dialogue.*
Completed
11. *MC to create a profile for the SeqCode on Bluesky and to investigate the use of a starter pack.*
Completed
12. *PH to contact Hauke Smidt to initiate discussions between Hauke and FV to establish a special category for species descriptions in ISME communications.*
FV, MC and Marike Palmer have been approached to serve as senior editors of ISME Communications to assist in promoting the use of the SeqCode for species descriptions as part of papers within the scope of the journal.
13. *KK, IS, MC and LMR to prepare mid-term reports from the commissions or working groups to be tabled at the next EB meeting.*
Ongoing, deadline for the mid-term reports will be 15 March 2025.
14. *KK to investigate possible RCN and ICB funding.*
Discussions with BW and ALR to look at possible grant applications will proceed. There is, however, a concern over the availability of Federal funding for such projects under the new administration in the US.
15. *KK to ask the Standards Working Group to discuss possible minimum recommendations for metadata linked to entries.*
Ongoing

4. Reports from Commissions and Working Groups

Legislative Commission

Version 1.1.0 of the SeqCode has now been posted on the Registry and ISME websites, as per the Statutes. Draft proposals for possible amendments to the code will be discussed by the Commission when these proposals have been finalised.

Standards Working Group

The working group will still meet to discuss the possibility of providing minimum recommendations for metadata linked to entries.

Registry and Nomenclature Working Group

At present 808 names have been validated which include 419 species. Another 227 names have been endorsed and could be validated once the taxon descriptions have been published. Marike Palmer is leading the development of guidelines for the consultation process with First Peoples when taxon names linked to their culture or language are proposed. The link to the Registry via NCBI's LinkOut has proven to be very valuable in directing interested parties to the registry.

Reconciliation Commission

The commission will soon have a meeting to discuss and monitor issues and developments such as the priority of names of higher taxa. An example is the phylum *Patescibacteriota* that will have priority over *Minisyncocota* based on the SeqCode.

5. Dialog between the ICSP, BISMis and the SeqCode

We are currently waiting for feedback from the Bergey's Manual Trust to hear if the discussion will go ahead.

6. Preparation of the annual report for ISME

Reports on the activities of all Commissions and Working Groups should be submitted to BW by 15 March 2025.

7. The future of the SeqCode after approval of Section 10

After a discussion on the possible impact of the approval of Section 10 of the ICNP on the SeqCode, it was decided to continue with this discussion at the next meeting when there might be greater clarity on how LPSN will implement the new rules. The EB strongly feels that we should continue to encourage the use of the SeqCode among taxonomists by highlighting the clear benefits of using the SeqCode.

8. Recording of SeqCode names on NCBI

After we had been made aware that NCBI staff referred to SeqCode names as illegitimate in an email, KK interacted with Conrad Schoch. He indicated that it was the wrong choice of wording and was not meant to be an official point of view. He also indicated that after it is clear how ICNP Section 10 will be implemented, names validated using the SeqCode could be indicated as such.

9. SeqCode presence on social media

MC created a profile for the SeqCode on BlueSky with the handle @seqcode.bsky.social.

10. Conference and Meeting Updates

EB members are encouraged to submit any relevant documents on the shared drive.

11. Definition of membership

LMR requested that the EB consider providing a more specific definition of SeqCode community membership to ensure that members are aligned with the goals of the SeqCode. It was decided to address this matter in future should the need become evident.

New action items

1. FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved.

Ongoing action items

2. PH to request the ISME Board to reconsider the requirement that ISME funding cannot be used for the payment of persons assisting with the development of the Registry.
3. FV to draft a text for a Wikipedia article on the SeqCode and circulated it amongst the EB.
4. BW to prepare a draft proposal for possible amendments to the code to include paratypes for further discussion by the EB.
5. KK, IS, MC and LMR to prepare mid-term reports from the commissions or working groups to be submitted on 15 March 2025.
6. KK to investigate possible RCN and ICB funding with BW and ALR as co-PIs.
7. KK to ask the Standards Working Group to discuss possible minimum recommendations for metadata linked to entries.

Minutes prepared by FV: 20 February 2025

Approved: 24 February 2025